

Why aren't students reading?

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Abstract

This micro study aimed to explore, "Why aren't our students reading?" For this study, I have chosen students from my school. Although the English language is a second language in the schools of the Bhutanese people and it is also given the paramount importance by the Education Ministry, it remains a national concern for many educators and parents in Bhutan. Most of the teachers and principals seem to believe that the majority of students lack reading skills. Students hardly read books other than prescribed texts. On the other hand, teachers have taught the reading strategies for our children to use and become competent and lifelong readers. In spite of all these efforts, we do not see many students display good at reading, which consequently hampers the acquisition of reading ability by students. I did a case study with thirty-six students of classes IV to XII. I collected my data using a focus group interview with students to have more in-depth information on the perspectives of reading. My study identified four main areas of concern.

Keywords: Bhutan, students, Education, national concern, educators, teachers

Introduction

Educational research provides valuable information and innovations in the field of classroom teaching. The languages of Bhutan carry a rich and diverse tradition of oral literature, but these genres and the cultural values they embody may disappear if they are not promoted. In Bhutan, schools are active sites for cultural preservation. For this reason, and also since English is the language of curricula for most subjects taught in school, we assumed that one of how Bhutan's diverse cultures can be Honoured and enlivened is through the study of folk literature in the English curriculum. Therefore, reading is a gateway to new ideas and is important for students' learning. Reading any form of literature is the basis for the literate individual to develop effective communication skills, both spoken and written. The ability to read is essential for being able to learn any subject taught in schools. Despite its importance, the students hardly value reading, and teachers hardly promote this trend in school.

The ultimate goal of reading is comprehension. It allows the reader to make sense of what the text is about. We must instill the importance of reading in our students to improve comprehension. Reading can help students achieve not only their academic needs but, more importantly, their life goals. According to McNamara (2007) [31], reading strategy refers

to the different cognitive and behavioural actions readers use to achieve comprehension in reading. The implementation of reading strategies in teaching and learning will increase the level of concentration and make learning becomes effective, leading to student success. For example, good readers distinguish between important information and details as they read and can use clues in the text to anticipate information and/or relate new information to information already stated. They are also able to notice inconsistencies in a text and employ strategies to make these inconsistencies understandable (Garner, 1980) [22]. Therefore, the research is intended to explore and find out factors that hinder the capability and confidence of the students in reading ability.

Although the English language is a second language in the schools of the Bhutanese people and it is also given paramount importance by the Education Ministry. It remains a national concern for many educators and parents in Bhutan. Most of the teachers and principals seem to believe that the majority of students lack reading skills. Students do reading in schools just for academic purposes. The Ministry of Education allocated a library budget to buy library books for every school to promote reading habits a few years back. However, the use of library books is minimal. By now, all the schools have adequate library books for all grade levels.

Students should cultivate reading habits to improve their growing literacy skills, including vocabulary and knowledge. In my experience as a teacher at a school for the last twenty-eight years, many students in the school do not like to read because they do not understand what they read. Students do reading in school just for academic purposes. Most of the students do not read books during their leisure hours. Students hardly read books other than prescribed texts. On the other hand, teachers have provided the necessary support for our children to use reading techniques and become competent and lifelong readers. Despite all these efforts, we do not see many students display good reading, consequently hampering the acquisition of reading ability by students. All these are indicators that show certain factors that hinder the capability and confidence of the students in reading ability.

As implied above, there are a range of reasons as to why this might be the case. Is it because students are not skilled enough to read? Is it because reading materials are not easily accessible? Is it because teachers do not explicitly teach the reading strategies? There could be many reasons, and the likely cause is a combination of these. Ahuja (2007) [6] states that today's youth is not educated until they become an effective reader. Thus, reading is the first button in the garment of education. The ability to read well is one of the most valuable skills in this ever-widening world. Today, reading serves a manifold purpose. It is needed in daily life activities. In this context, as a teacher at a school, it was the biggest concern to explore why students are not able to read books effectively and efficiently. In this context, as a teacher, it was the biggest concern to explore why students aren't reading. My study identified nine main areas of concern.

Reading comprehension

Many students have difficulty comprehending what they read. Knowing how to read words has ultimately little value if the student is unable to construct meaning from the text (Klinger, Vaughn, & Boardman, 2007) [28]. Comprehension is a process in which readers filter understanding through the lens of their motivation, knowledge, cognitive abilities, and experiences. Effective readers have a purpose for reading and use their background knowledge and experiences to relate to the text: readers don't comprehend unless they draw connections between what they read and their background knowledge (Tankersley, 2003) [37]. Furthermore, Pang *et al.* (2003) [43] describe reading comprehension as an active process a reader makes to construct meaning from a text. This process consists of using an interaction between prior knowledge and drawing inferences from the different words and expressions the writer uses to comprehend information, ideas, and viewpoints. Smith (1985) [1] also believes that reading comprehension involves bringing prior knowledge to interact with what she/he is reading so that he/she can achieve comprehension. On the other hand, comprehension is a complex process that includes more than "just listening to the words decoded" (Duke & Pearson, 2002, p. 232) [18]. It consists of various processes requiring the use of different strategies in different contexts to meet the demands of the text. Thus, observing how students comprehend a text and preparing a training program accordingly is challenging.

Reading Strategies

Reading strategies are methods or procedures readers may use to gain a better understanding of what they are reading. Once readers learned to utilize effective reading strategies, they can apply the strategies regularly depending on the demand of the text (Wangsgard, 2010) [41]. In the study of Wangsgard (2010) [41], it was found that non-effective readers did not apply strategies as they read a text; instead, the non-effective readers saw it as a hindrance rather than learning something new. Effective readers understand when and how to use reading strategies before, during, and after reading. However, helping students develop the use of effective reading strategies has proven to be challenging due to several reasons (Grabe & Stoller, 2002) [23]. It is assumed that a lack of practising different reading strategies affects the enhancement of the reading ability of children. Teaching children reading strategies will help them feel confident and read fluently. Kilfoil (1998) [29] says that students should be taught strategies that would enable them to become independent learners and readers and also to cope when they experience difficulty during reading. Therefore, reading strategies are essential not only to successful comprehension but to overcoming reading problems and becoming a better reader.

Learning environment

According to Schoenfeld, Smith, and Arcavi (1993) [34], a learning environment comprises teachers, existing curricula, instructional equipment, as well as the institutional and larger learner community. Therefore, creating a classroom environment that is conducive to learning is vital, as learning mostly takes place in the classroom, and a large amount of a child's time is spent sitting in a classroom. Alvermann, Gillis, and Phelps (2012) [2] assert that learning will be influenced by the context in which it takes place. A student's school experience will be shaped in part by the school setting. Therefore, a conducive classroom environment is an important place in the growth of a child, and it is important to understand how to affect this environment to receive maximum effectiveness in instruction. According to Brophy (1999) [3], a positive classroom environment does not just happen; the teacher needs to create it. The classroom should also have space for displaying teaching-learning materials, setting book corners, and walking freely around the group. Overcrowding in the classroom will affect the quality of a student's education.

Parents' background and the home Environment

The home environment is a very important factor affecting lifelong readers. Parents are the child's first educators. A child's family and home environment have a strong impact on his/her language and literacy development and educational achievement. This impact is stronger during the child's early years but continues throughout their school year. The support, guidance, and literacy skills of parents will have an impact on their children's reading ability. M. C. Smith & Elish-Piper (2002) [5] mention that whenever parents have literacy problems, the potential exists for their children to struggle with literacy acquisition. Parents reading to babies and young children have a strong impact on children's language and literacy development. A parent reading to their children in the preschool years is regarded

as an important predictor of literacy achievement (Weinberger, 1996) [7]. Therefore, there are two components to the role parents play in reading attitude. First, the home literacy culture is significant to the development of children. Within the home literacy environment, there should be the presence of literacy artifacts, including many different kinds of printed materials.

Motivation to learn to read

The other important factor responsible for developing a reading interest in students depends on motivation. Day and Bamford (1998) [16] state that motivation is a force that makes people do or not do something. Wigfield and Guthrie (2000) [24] mention that motivation and engagement make reading enjoyable. The greater the motivation, the greater the learning will be. Therefore, students need to be motivated to be learning. One of the reasons for students' poor reading habits may be due to the lack of teachers' appropriate motivation towards teaching reading skills. It plays an important role and brings behavioral changes and influences in the learners. Motivation is something that energizes, directs, and sustains behavior; it gets students moving, points them in a particular direction, and keeps them going (Ormrod, 2014) [9]. Motivated to learn also refers to, "The degree to which students are dedicated to and engaged in learning. A willingness to think through problems and work through challenges to achieve mastery of a concept or skill goes beyond simply having fun during learning." In this sense, not all learners are at the same cognitive level of learning. Teachers should identify the learner's intelligence level and reinforce the learning accordingly. Kennedy, as cited in Ions & Quigley (1995) [10], said that not every child has an equal talent or an equal ability or equal motivation, but children have the equal right to develop their talent, their ability, and their motivation.

Reading materials

If the reading material is interesting, learners take the initiative to read with enthusiasm, and retention will be quicker and more permanent. Zangmo (2002) [44] mentions that many studies have shown and supported the notion that a book-rich classroom environment will increase the motivation levels of children to read. Winch (2004) [14] suggests that we offer students a print environment within which to interact. Engage students with surrounding print as both readers and writers. The IEA report on the study of reading in 32 countries during the late 90s, as mentioned by Elley (cited in Zangmo, 2002) [44], shows that the size of the school or classroom libraries differentiated education systems that produced high literacy scores. Similarly, Elley (cited in Zangmo, 2002) [44] posits that 'ready access to a wider range of books is key in raising the level' (p.36). Therefore, the availability of books is a key factor in reading development.

Teacher Modeling

Modelling refers to the patterning of thoughts, beliefs, strategies, and actions after those displayed by one or more models-usually teachers or parents who explain and demonstrate skills (Schunk & Zimmerman, 1997) [43]. Mana and Misheff (as cited in Oğuz, Yıldız, & Hayır-sever, 2009) [32] suggest that the joy and enthusiasm of reading cannot be

taught but modeled. Accordingly, students could not only become good readers through modelling. The role of the teacher in the school is paramount. Research suggests that the frequency with which students read in and out of school depends upon the priority classroom teachers give to independent reading (Anderson, Wilson, & Fielding, 1988) [4]. For a student to be a better reader, a role model provided by parents, teachers, and peers may facilitate their learning. Gam-brell, Morrow, & Pressley (2007) [21] state that students need to see that we value reading and that reading is important in our lives. Therefore, teacher modelling and parent modelling of reading have a positive effect on student learning to read effectively.

Culture and home factors

Reading is seen as 'work' by both parents and children, and thus reading for pleasure hardly takes place in some families and cultures in the context of remote places in Bhutan. Besides, illiterate parents and elders in homes cannot understand the value of reading. The society at large follows an oral culture in remote places of Bhutan. People prefer to talk rather than read. The IEA Reading Literacy Study found that students whose home language differed from the school language performed less well on the reading tests than those who were tested in their home language (cited in Zangmo, 2002) [44].

Voluminous Syllabus and Time Constraint

The literature distinguishes the term syllabus from the curriculum. "Syllabus is a plan of what is to be achieved through our teaching and our students' learning" (Garner, 1980) [22] and it focuses on the way the contents are chosen and graded (Nunan, 1988) [17] while "curriculum" is concerned with how education programs are designed, implemented, assessed, managed, and delivered (Nunan, 1988) [17]. The curriculum is very broad, and the syllabus is a smaller part of the curriculum (Hosney, 2013) [19]. However, a heavy syllabus can create a sense of pressure and urgency to cover all the required material quickly. This may lead to superficial reading practices, such as skimming and scanning. Thus, students may struggle to fully comprehend and analyze what they are reading. This can hinder their ability to think critically, make connections, and extract meaningful insights from the text.

Time management plays a vital role in improving students' academic performance and achievements. There is no one right way to manage our time; however, it is important to get to know ourselves, so we can make good decisions about how to use our time. Time management is extremely important, especially when it comes to students, because it will boost their grades and enhance their productivity (Laurie & Hellsten, 2002) [20]. However, most of the time, students face problems like task aversion and uncertainty, so they start to procrastinate because they lack organizational skills. As a result, students will not be able to organize duties according to their priorities, so they get distracted easily, ending up procrastinating. As we can see, time management is quite essential to any student, and it is one of the keys to higher academic achievements (Kelly, 2004) [25].

Ethical Issues

Ethical issues are the professional code of conduct that

researchers must abide by before, during, and after the research. A Guide to Research Ethics (2003) ^[43] of the University of Minnesota provides us with very important reasons why understanding research ethics is important. According to the Guide, Research is a public trust that must be ethically conducted, trustworthy, and socially responsible if the results are to be valuable. All parts of a research project – from the project design to the submission of the results for peer review have to be upstanding to be considered ethical. When even one part of a research project is questionable or conducted unethically, the integrity of the entire project is called into question. (pg. 6-7). Therefore, the researcher will take care of any potential ethical issues. While carrying out the study, the researcher will maintain the confidentiality of interviewees. In the pre-data collection, the researcher will be aware of how should get access to the data collection. For instance, getting approvals from the concerned authorities, such as HRC, Mongar Dzongkhag, Ministry of Education, District Education Officers, and the school principal, and also asking interviewees to fill in the consent form in advance to ensure full participation for the collection of data. During the data collection, confidentiality and anonymity of the views responded by participants will be maintained throughout the research. All the participants would be guaranteed not to disclose their identity, and pseudonyms will be provided in the final write-up. Similarly, during the post-data collection period, the researcher will maintain the participants' identities and ensure that the participants' views and ideas are protected from any damage or harm. Any information regarding the researcher, such as field notes, interview transcripts, and observation sheets, will be kept securely, and it will be available only to the researcher.

Findings of the study

Reading is an important activity in the process of learning. In the movement of human society, it has been given a greater importance and has become one of the essential aspects of the functioning of human beings, who are collectively involved in the regulation of society and the exposure of knowledge and revelation of a literate society. Reading involves people's participation and growth in a literate society. So, reading shapes a good personality, ideas, right thinking, and attitude change. Given that one of the most important goals of teaching reading is to help our students develop as strategic and independent readers. Strategies should be taught through direct explanation, explicit teacher modeling, and extensive feedback. In addition, students should never be in doubt as to what the strategies are, where and when they can be used, and how they are used. More importantly, they should be informed of the value and usefulness of strategies in reading. This is proved by the results of the participants said that how to learn reading techniques during the primary level is important for the promotion of reading ability because it helps to build their vocabularies and lays the foundations to become independent readers, and also makes reading more engaging and fun for them.

The study found that the unavailability of reading materials and facilities in the school is one of the major concerns of students. Thus, access to the availability of reading materials can be an important factor that hinders the

enhancement of students' reading ability. According to Zangmo (2002) ^[44], who revealed that many studies have shown and supported the notion that a book-rich classroom environment will increase the motivation levels of the children to read. The study also reveals that the lack of supplementary reading materials in the school deters students from building their reading abilities. Generally, this factor has become a common issue in all schools, and it has affected the students to read well with accuracy and fluency. It seems that supplementary reading materials that meet students' interests are rarely found in remote schools, although the school has adequate library books. Therefore, lack of access to a wide range of materials hampers the acquisition of vocabulary and comprehension skills in addition to the development of reading habits. In school, it is not possible to get an adequate number of interesting reading materials because of limited financial support. Even if the schools have the subject matter and illustrations available, many of the imported books are often unfamiliar to the cultural backgrounds of readers. This lack of resources could also be a reason why students do not show interest in reading, and thus, their reading habits are very poor.

Research has shown that if learners' reading interest is weak, the competency of the students grows little and their quality as readers diminishes (Guthrie, McRae, & Klauda, 2007) ^[27]. Personal interest matters a lot in learning any type of language skills. Students do reading in school just for academic purposes. Students hardly read books other than prescribed texts. We hardly find them taking books to read during their free time. This problem in children indicates a lack of interest in reading. Therefore, students need to be motivated to be learning, and it plays an important role and brings behavioral changes and influences in the learners.

Parents' support plays a vital role in students' academic performance, especially in reading. Navsaria and Kathard (2011) ^[30] found that teachers have observed that learners who received support from their parents improved academic achievement at school, and conversely, a lack of support from home harmed learners. The study indicated that the literacy skills of parents played a vital role in children. It was found that all the participants who participated in this study had parents with literacy problems that made them struggle with literacy acquisition. Most of the participants demonstrated that they had limited exposure to the world of books before entering formal school. Some schools are in remote settings where the number of illiterate parents is larger than the educated ones, and many parents are not able to help their children in their studies. On a similar note, the participants in this study believed that children should be given exposure to books and encouraged to cultivate a love for reading. Teachers could increase students' exposure to media by allowing them to use cell phones and watch television programs related to learning to read.

The study found that the majority of the student participants expressed that reading at home after school hours is minimal, as they are mainly occupied with household activities such as washing, fetching water, collecting firewood, and so on. In the school, they get very little time to read, and there is limited reading material available in the class. Moreover, they hardly get adequate support and guidance from teachers to read other reading materials than

the prescribed reading text.

Students do not display a high awareness of reading strategies. The idea of strategy is rather vague to them. Nevertheless, they describe what actions they adopt to overcome their reading problems. When reading a text, the majority of learners report proceeding by reading the whole text to get a general idea instead of previewing it by using the strategy of skimming and then scanning.

Helping students develop the use of effective reading strategies has proven to be challenging for several reasons (Grabe & Stoller, 2002) [23]. First, comprehension is a complex process that includes more than “just listening to the words decoded” (Duke & Pearson, 2002, p. 232) [18]. It consists of various processes requiring the use of different strategies in different contexts to meet the demands of the text. Thus, observing how students comprehend a text and preparing a training program accordingly is challenging. Second, individual differences have a great effect on strategy instruction. That is, a strategy that works well for a group of particular students may not be effective for others due to different experiences in reading, age, or proficiency level. Third, being a strategic reader does not mean knowing and employing a single strategy for a particular task. Nor does it mean using all the instructed strategies at once. Rather, strategic reading requires students to arrange the use of various strategies by changing texts, purposes, and goals (Grabe & Stoller, 2002) [23]. In this study, such challenges were not disclosed by any of the participants. However, the study found out some of the pertinent factors that hinder students in reading ability are non-availability of the materials, vast syllabus, home environment, lack of interest, and Parents’ background. Although there are several difficulties and problems faced in reading. The results revealed were only from the student's point of view. Therefore, the importance of reading needs to be emphasized in school.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study makes the following recommendations:

Recommendation for the Ministry of Education and Skill Development (MoESD)

Since the MoESD is the main stakeholder in this regard, the ministry should carry out an in-depth study to find out the impact of reading on students’ reading ability and what are some of the difficulties and problems faced by both teachers and students. The findings of this study revealed that there are some difficulties and problems faced by students. According to the Bhutan Programme for International Student Assessment for Development (PISA-D) National Report in consultation with MoE, the Royal Education Council (REC) and Royal University of Bhutan (RUB) reported that poor reading habits among the Bhutanese isn’t something that comes as a surprise. The recent findings of (PISA-D) assessment show that poor reading literacy among students hinders their academic performance. The finding is also not new. Past studies have shown that our students are unable to comprehend the meaning of the texts to answer questions correctly. The findings show, there is a need to cultivate and instill the habit of reading among children, and schools should enhance students’ reading and

comprehension skills to improve their academic performance across the subjects.

MoESD also needs to work closely with REC regarding the thinning of the curriculum, because the concern about the coverage of the syllabus greatly affects the teachers in the choice of their reading strategies in this research. According to the participants, the syllabus was very vast; they were not able to use a reading strategy to enhance students’ reading ability. Another area of concern is the lack of reading materials, although the Ministry of Education has allocated a library budget to buy library books for every school to promote reading habits in the past. Now it has stopped for the past few years. It would be helpful if MoESD provided the same library budget to schools as before to have adequate library books for all grade levels.

The study found the importance of reading strategies in teaching and learning. Therefore, MoESD, in close consultation and collaboration with relevant agencies, should provide necessary workshops, training, and seminar opportunities for the teachers.

Recommendation for the Dzongkhag Education Sector

The findings of this study revealed that the need for an appropriate reading strategy used in classroom teaching by teachers can promote reading. However, on the other hand ineffective teacher is not competent enough to handle the use of reading strategies in his/her teaching. Therefore, the Dzongkhag Education Sector should provide resources and necessary teacher professional courses/workshops and training. The conduct of Cluster-Based In-service Program (CPIP) and Dzongkhag-based In-service Programs (DBIP) needs to be intensified, focusing on student-centered teaching strategies so that overall change occurs in school instructional culture. It should be focused on the improvement of students’ learning to read, with the improvement of teachers’ classroom delivery strategies.

Recommendation for the Schools/Principals

The school principals concerned invigorate instructional leadership roles and accordingly plan and develop professional development programs for teachers. The schools need to organize orientation programs for teachers to re-emphasize the importance of reading strategies, besides the orientation on the entire subject. The professional programs that could be conducted are the Orientation Workshop on Reading Strategies and Factors that Affect the Acquisition of reading ability in the form of a School-Based In-service program (SBIP). The school must also arrange supplementary reading materials in the class so that students can easily access them. In school, it is becoming quite a major issue in many academic institutions that students tend to depend on lecture notes rather than visiting the library for information. Therefore, the school principals should caution faculty staff to prepare only handouts for students, and they will complement them with further research in the library. Additionally, the respective school-level monitor and the principal must ensure that teachers organize their lessons using a variety of reading strategies with a focus on promoting reading ability. Students would spend more time on reading if reading activities are actively promoted and a reading atmosphere is created in school. Thus, schools need to organize reading

competitions among students and offer awards to encourage reading.

Recommendation for the Parents

This study revealed that one of the reasons for the lack of reading ability in students is due to a lack of support and guidance from parents at home. Parents' active participation in reading at home would promote students' interest in reading. On the contrary, if parents participate less in their children's reading activities, students tend to spend less time on reading. Therefore, it is recommended that parents should help their children cultivate reading skills when they are young, so that it becomes part and parcel of their lives. Today, there are many community libraries where children can be encouraged to go and read novels and fiction. When this is done, it will help them express themselves well and write good English, which will eventually lead to better academic performance.

On the other hand, the heads of the schools could encourage parents with low literacy levels to be more aware of the importance of reading at home, so they could better support their children by providing a certain time for reading every evening and morning.

Recommendation for the Teachers

Reading is a useful skill across the curriculum. We must explicitly teach the reading strategies for our children to use and become competent and lifelong readers. Teaching reading is not the responsibility of the language teacher alone. All the teachers across the curriculum must incorporate reading activities in their respective subjects. This study has shown that learners who receive strategy training generally learn better than those who do not. Educationists say that students were found to read the content without understanding the meaning of the text. One of the main reasons for this was the poor reading habits among students. It found that poor reading literacy affected students' performance in science and mathematics because they were unable to understand the language (PISA-D assessment 2019) [45]. Therefore, teachers are directly responsible for the students' learning. Teachers need to build an adequate foundation in reading skills by developing reading habits right from the lower grades and at a young age. This must be achieved by implementing a child-centered teaching strategy, making teaching and learning more relevant, challenging, and interesting as per the needs of students. Additionally, while presenting strategies for students to use, teachers should use a three-step process of instruction. Firstly, give explicit instructions on what the strategy is, why it is used, when it is used, and how to use it effectively. Second, model the use of the strategy, and thirdly, provide several structured opportunities for students to practice the use of the strategy in authentic content-reading situations.

Conclusion

Right from the start, this study has been an academic journey, especially for a novice writer like me. It has been an enriching journey that enabled me to explore deeper into students' views on reading.

The study aimed to explore the factors that hinder the capability and confidence of the students in reading ability

in my school. It is the teachers' responsibility to train students to determine their own goals and strategies and how to use all these strategies according to their levels, interests, and needs. Teachers need to provide explicit instruction about both skills and strategies. Through strategies, teachers can also help the students to maintain their motivation, autonomy, and confidence, and keep on going and try to accomplish the goal of learning the target language. In this regard, teachers need to incorporate language learning strategies into their teaching methods and approaches, train the students to apply the appropriate strategy for a specific purpose or a specific skill area, and encourage them to use the strategies as frequently as possible. Students can learn to use language learning strategies to improve their language skills. Last but not least, as was found in this study, parents' active participation in reading at home would promote students' interest in reading. Therefore, the heads of the schools and teachers could encourage parents with low literacy levels to be more aware of the importance of reading at home, so they could better support their children by providing a certain time for reading every evening and morning.

In general, the findings of this study provided useful information for teachers to use effective reading strategies in their teaching and learning, especially in developing good reading skills and abilities among students. Therefore, to future researchers, it is recommended that nationwide research on the impact of reading ability on students be carried out. Since not many researchers or any analytical studies have been conducted so far in these areas, it is expected that through such a study, there will be more possibility of understanding the process of developing reading habits in our children.

Since the study focused only on my schools, it limits the possibility of generalizing the findings. Students' and teachers' views and opinions were not representative of all the students and teachers in the country. Therefore, the findings of this study cannot be generalized to the whole country. The inclusion of a large number of respondents covering a wide range of school students, teachers, and parents' views would have added significance to this study. This study was the first of its kind done by the researcher. Therefore, at any cost, the researcher had no intention to expose the shortcomings and limitations of the teachers and the students involved in the research. Rather, this study is intended for the professional development of the self and their fellow teachers by sharing the literature and the findings.

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